
Learning Transformation: Collaboration and Problem Solving through Project Based Learning on the Human Respiratory System at Public High School 1 Teluk Batang

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Abstract: This research study aimed to investigate the implementation of Project Based Learning (PjBL) on students' problem-solving abilities and collaborative skills in the context of learning the respiratory system. The study was conducted at Public High School 1 Teluk Batang, West Kalimantan, Indonesia, involving grade XI science students. The research method used in this study is a quantitative method using Posttest Only Control Group Designs. The experimental group received instruction using the PjBL model, while the control group followed a conventional teaching approach. Data collection methods included observation, posttests, and photo documentation. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and quantitative analysis, including t-tests for comparing the experimental and control groups. The results showed that the implementation of PjBL significantly improved students' problem-solving abilities and collaborative skills compared to the conventional teaching approach. The PjBL model provided students with practical experiences, teamwork opportunities, and real-world problem-solving tasks, enabling them to develop critical, creative, communicative, and collaborative skills. The findings of this study contribute to the understanding of effective learning methods in the context of evolving educational needs and provide guidance for teachers and policymakers in improving teaching practices. The study emphasizes the importance of equipping students with strong problem-solving and collaborative abilities to face the challenges of the industrial revolution 5.0.

Keyword: Project Based Learning (PjBL), Collaboration, Problem Solving

Introduction

Education is the key to developing students' abilities in facing future challenges in the era of the industrial revolution 5.0. Lecturers and teachers are expected to be able to teach students to master various skills through the lecture process, field trips (Ariyansyah, 2018), creating blog-based learning media (Nawawi et al., 2021), and practicum (Sulistiany & Darmawan, 2020). In this rapidly evolving era, students need to be equipped with strong collaborative and problem-solving skills. Therefore, there needs to be a transformation in learning methods that can encourage the development of these skills effectively.

Learning model that w considered effective in building collaborative and problem-solving skills is Project Based Learning (PjBL). This model emphasizes practical experience where students engage in authentic projects or tasks involving teamwork, solving real problems, and applying knowledge in real-world contexts. Through this model, students are expected to develop critical, creative, communicative, and collaborative skills (Septikasari & Frasandy, 2018). Similar opinions were conveyed (Hasanah et al., 2021) projects can help students develop their solutions, critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In project-based learning, students are often asked to set goals and develop action plans to achieve those goals (Rahmazatullaili et al., 2017). The process of creating schedules and action plans can help students develop their ability to plan and organize their work.

Pre-observation research activities have been carried out on June 24, 2022 at Public High School 1 Teluk Batang, North Kayong Regency, West Kalimantan Province, information was obtained that biology subject teachers in schools have obstacles in learning, namely; 1) lack of biology learning aids and learning media; 2) Teachers still apply learning with lecture methods or teacher-centered learning while the Indonesian government currently wants student-centered learning where learning can be done using an independent curriculum. Meanwhile, based on the results of previous research, information was obtained that learning with the lecture method where the teacher is still the center of knowledge has various weaknesses including; the presentation of material is less interesting for students because students only become listeners, and students are not involved in the learning process, this causes the material presented to be easily forgotten by students (Devi et al., 2015). Students become bored, because in class only record what the teacher conveys, (Zunaidah & Sulistiyowati, 2020). Meanwhile (Hodiyanto et al., 2020) said that Teachers still lack in applying varied learning models such as the application of project-based models.

Based on the results of pre-observation that have been carried out, this study aims to investigate the implementation of the Project Based Learning learning model on problem-solving skills and collaborative abilities on respiratory system material in humans at Public High School 1 Teluk Batang. In the context of learning respiratory system material, grade XI students will engage in projects that demand collaboration, analysis, and problem solving. This research was expected to contribute as a good practice of learning in public schools in West Kalimantan, Indonesia and especially in the application of PBL learning models on respiratory system material in humans. In addition, the results of this study can provide guidance for teachers and policy makers in improving existing learning methods to meet today's evolving educational needs.

Method

The research method used in this study is a quantitative method using Posttest Only Control Group Designs. This research was conducted on grade XI science students at Public High School 1 Teluk Batang, with a total of two classes, namely XI Science 1 as an experimental class and XI Science 2 as a control class. To select the research sample, a saturated sampling technique was used where all students from both classes were included in this study.

The data collection techniques used include observation, posttest, and photo documentation of activities. The instruments used in this study consisted of interview sheets, questionnaires, and tests. Observations are made to observe student and teacher interactions and see the extent to which students are able to collaborate and solve problems in the context of PBL learning. Posttest is used to measure students' problem-solving ability and collaborative ability after learning using the PBL model. In addition, documentation in the form of photos is also taken to support data analysis and enrich research reports. The collected data will be analyzed using a difference test (t-test) using spss 25.0 to compare the results between the experimental and control groups. The data that has been obtained is then analyzed descriptively and quantitatively.

Results and Discussion

This research has been carried out at SMA N 1 Teluk Batang, North Kayong Regency, West Kalimantan Province, with the aim of investigating the effect of the application of the Project Based Learning (PjBL) model on students' ability to solve problems and collaborate. This study involved students of grade XI IPA 1 and XI IPA 2 as research subjects, with XI IPA 1 as an experimental class and XI IPA 2 as a control class. The number of students in each class is 32. The research data was obtained through post-test results and questionnaires that measured the problem-solving ability and collaborative ability of students at SMA N 1 Teluk Batang. The implementation of the PJBL model in this study will be carried out in January 2023.

In this study, the PjBL model was chosen as an innovative learning approach, because students are involved in solving projects that require real problem solving and collaboration between students. The data obtained will be analyzed to evaluate the impact of the PjBL model on students' problem-solving and collaborative abilities. The results of this study are expected to provide valuable insights in improving learning at SMA N 1 Teluk Batang and a broader contribution to overall educational practice. Data on problem-solving capabilities and collaborative capabilities in experimental and control classes can be seen in table 1 and table 2.

Table 1. Problem Solving Ability of SMA N 1 Teluk Batang Students

Troubleshooting Ability Indicator	Experimental Class	Control Class
Problem statement	91%	82%
Developing hypotheses	85%	75%
Testing hypotheses	82%	70%
Develop and draw conclusions	77%	64%
Applying conclusions	73%	63%
Average	81%	71%

Table 2. Collaborative Ability of SMA N 1 Teluk Batang Students

Collaborative Capability Indicator	Experimental Class	Control Class
Accountability and Personal Responsibility of Individuals	92%	71%
Face-to-face Interaction	84%	70%
Positive interdependence	74%	66%
Communication Skills	88%	74%
Group Work Skills	79%	72%
Average	83%	70%

Based on the results of the data normality test in the experimental class and control class using SPSS 25.0, it is known that the problem-solving ability data has a sig value of $0.200 > 0.00$, then the data is declared normally distributed. While collaborative capability data has a value of $0.200 > 0.00$ so that the data is declared normally distributed. Then the data that has been obtained is then tested for homogeneity, where Sig values are obtained $0.148 > 0.05$ so that the data on problem solving ability is homogeneous. As for collaborative ability data, Sig values of $0.871 > 0.05$ were obtained, so that the data was declared homogeneous. Based on the calculation results, it is known that the class data is normally distributed and homogeneous, then continued with parametric statistics using the T test (t-test polled variance) with SPSS 25. The results of the T test (t-test polled variance) can be seen in table3.

Table 3. Results of hypothesis test of problem-solving ability and collaborative ability.

Information	Statistical T-test (t-test polled variance)	Conclusion
Troubleshooting Ability	Sig 0,04	$0,04 < 0,05$ There is a significant difference
Collaborative capabilities	Sig 0,00	$0,00 < 0,05$ There is a significant difference

Based on the observations that have been made, it can be seen that students began to collaborate when the project was distributed to students. Students who had gathered according to their groups began to discuss to solve the problems given by the teacher, where the teacher asked each group to make a 3 (Three) Dimensional teaching aids about the human respiratory system. The discussion process to the percentage of project results can be seen in figure 1. While the results of 3D media of the human respiratory system made by students in the experimental class can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 1. Implementation of making 3-Dimensional (3D) media of the human respiratory system in the Experimental Class

Figure 2. 3D Products of the Human Respiratory System in the Experimental Class

Based on the results of the problem-solving ability test that has been carried out, it can be seen that the Project Based Learning (PjBL) learning model can improve problem-solving skills. This can be seen from the results of problem-solving ability test scores in the experimental class which tend to be better than in the control class and the results showed that the experimental class that applied PjBL had a higher average problem-solving score compared to the control class that applied the conventional model. This suggests that PjBL can improve student problem solving. This opinion is in line with (Aksela & Haatainen, 2019) The use of Project Based Learning in teaching, will be very useful for teachers in overcoming boredom in learning, as well as being one of the strategies that can be applied in the classroom. A similar opinion was also expressed by (Jawaid et al., 2020) The learning process using Project Based Learning in making robots when integrated with Collaborative Learning can affect the ability in critical thinking, problem solving, independent learning, collaboration of students who take robotics courses.

The analysis in this study used questionnaires as a measure of collaborative ability, while the results of collaborative ability applied with the Project Based Learning (PjBL) model had an average percentage value of 77% and collaborative ability applied by conventional models had an average value of 63%. It is also known that the average value per highest indicator of collaborative ability applied with the Project Based Learning (PjBL) model is accountability and responsibility for individual problems with an average experimental class of 91% while the average per highest indicator of collaborative ability applied with conventional models is communication skills with an average percentage of 74%.

The results of the study obtained showed that the experimental class that applied PjBL had better collaborative abilities compared to the control class. This is because the implementation of project-based learning (PjBL) involves students in real projects that require cooperation and collaboration between students. In this context, students learn to communicate, work together, and share responsibility for achieving project goals, this increases students' ability to work effectively in teams then in Project Based Learning (PjBL), students depend on each other to achieve project goals. They recognize that their individual contributions are important to the overall success of the project, encouraging students to work collaboratively, helping each other, and valuing each other's contributions. By involving students in real projects, assignment distribution, interaction and discussion, positive interdependence, and the development of communication skills, PjBL creates an environment that encourages and enhances students' collaborative abilities. Students learn to work in teams, appreciate the role and contribution of each member, and develop essential communication skills in group work so that Project Based Learning (PjBL) learning can improve collaborative skills.

Project Based Learning (PjBL) indirectly makes students look more active in participating in learning, play a very active role in groups, and dare to express opinions and be able to find solutions in solving a problem experienced so as to make learning outcomes improve better. This opinion is in line with (Saputra et al., 2019) those who state that one way to train students' critical thinking is to provide problems to be solved both individually and in groups. Meanwhile (Asiyah et al., 2021) improved problem-solving ability will affect students' cognitive abilities.

To see if there are differences in problem-solving ability and collaborative ability after the Project Based Learning (PjBL) model in the experimental class compared to problem-solving ability and collaborative ability after applying the conventional learning model at SMA N 1 Teluk Batang, using the t test. Data normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, problem solving ability and collaborative ability are normally distributed, and homogeneity test using Levene test, problem solving ability and collaborative ability both data are declared homogeneous.

After knowing the data on normal and homogeneous problem-solving ability and collaborative ability, the hypothesis test will continue using the t-test pooled variance with the significance value of problem-solving ability in the experimental class and the control class is 0.04, which means less than 0.05. Therefore, the hypothetical results show that there is a significant difference in problem-solving ability between the experimental class and the control class. Moreover, the significance value of collaborative ability in the experimental class and the control class is 0.00, which is also much smaller than 0.05. This suggests a significant difference in collaborative ability between the two groups. In the context of decision making, the null hypothesis (H_0) states that there is no significant difference between the experimental group and the control group in problem-solving ability and collaborative ability. However, with significance values smaller than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. That is, there are significant differences between the experimental group and the control group in both abilities, based on these results, it can be concluded that the application of the PjBL model has a significant impact on improving students' problem-solving abilities and collaborative abilities.

In the context of education, improved problem-solving skills and collaborative abilities have important value, as both abilities become integral in preparing students for real-world challenges. The PjBL model can provide a learning environment that supports the development of both skills through an emphasis on real projects, collaboration, and reflection on learning experiences. Based on the results of the t-test, it was found that there was a real difference between collaboration ability and problem-solving ability in the experimental class and the control class, this could be due to the use of the PjBL method which requires students to be together in making media, as well as all students in active groups to discuss solving a problem. This opinion is reinforced by the results of research (Barron & Hammond, 2008) showing that PjBL can improve students' problem-solving skills and collaborative skills. They found that students who engaged in collaboration-based projects showed significant improvements in their ability to analyze problems, formulate strategies, and cooperate with others. Another opinion was also explained by (Kholifah & Hariastuti, 2022)

collaboration between students makes it easier to exchange ideas or ideas or ideas and also feelings when in a group to solve problems together.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study and the analysis provided, it can be concluded that the application of the PjBL model has a significant positive impact on improving students' problem-solving abilities and collaborative skills in Senior High School 1 Teluk Batang, West Kalimantan Province, Indonesia.

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